

Development of PVTGs in Jharkhand (India) and Annual Budget 2023-24

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ABSTRACT:

Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) are the smaller and most vulnerable segment of the tribal group. They are living a tranquil and homogeneous life in dispersed habitats. They are not having for access to proper education, health care, economy and social security. Currently India is having 75 such groups scattered in 18 states and 1 union territory. There are many schemes and plans being implemented by the developmental organisations of India under the aegis of Ministry of Tribal Affairs. Those schemes are for socio-economic upliftment. Conservation-cum-Development (CCD), has focused on the holistic development of PVTGs by giving more emphasis on infrastructure and human development. The method of community organisations is being followed to achieve the major objectives of the plan so that the problems. These problems can be resolved on the basis of the true identification of needs by the concerned level of Gram Sabha. The recent budget 2023-24 has shown positive sign towards the upliftment of PVTGs of India. Three new schemes are launched here. They are Pradhan Mantri PVTG Development Mission, National Sickle Cell Elimination Mission and Central Recruitment of Teachers for EMRSs by the allocation of around 15000 crore rupees to the ministry of tribal affairs. This paper will analyse the recent and past developmental programmes being implemented by the developmental organisations in India keeping in view of PVTGs of Jharkhand.

Keywords: PVTGs, Schemes, Budget 2023-24, Development

Introduction and Background of PVTGs

The Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) are more prone to backwardness socially and economically. Their population is aging or stagnating, they have low literacy rates,

primitive agricultural technologies, and they are economically backward. They typically live in isolated areas with weak administrative assistance and infrastructure. Primitive Tribal Groups (PTGs), the least advanced among the tribal community, were established as a distinct category of tribal groups by the Dhebar Commission in 1973. When the Dhebar committee recommended a new name for this group of people in 1973 to aid them, they were given the term 'Primitive Tribal Group' (PTG). The GOI agreed to their request, and in 1975 this legislation became enforceable. At the time, there were 54 PVTG. Their number of primitive tribal groups increased from 54 to 63 between 1992 and 1993. Primitive Tribal Group (PTG), which was officially recognized on the Dhebar Committee's proposal, was renamed as Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Group in 2006 bringing the total number of PVTGs in the country to 75, which are dispersed across 18 states and one Union Territory (Andaman & Nicobar Islands) as per 2011 census. Odisha has the most PVTGs (13), followed by Andhra Pradesh (12), 9 groups in Jharkhand and Bihar, out of the 75 listed PVTGs (Nandy, 2013). PVTGs are individuals whose way of life and customs are distinct from those of other STs; these individuals are not included in any other unique GOI program. These folks tend to reside distant from the major city and avoid mingling with other members of the community and each one has their own unique identity, language, and way of life. The name of the organization/department was changed from PTGs to PVTGs by the Government of India in 2006. A plan for the development of primitive tribal groups was also implemented in 2008, and the number of these groups climbed from 54 in 1973 to 75 in 2008, the largest number in Assam and Odisha, Bihar (Sahu, 2019). A distinct characteristic of most of the PVTGs are that usually they live in small habitations. Secondly, they greatly differ in terms of education level, economic situation and socio-cultural life. Their conditions were pathetic. Therefore, to provide them benefits of development in all aspects of life number of schemes have been worked out both by Government of India as well as by different state governments to minimise the problems and Issues of the PVTGs (Pancholi, 2018). This year, in budget session 2023-24, PVTGs have been given special attention after the launch of three schemes by the Finance Minister of India, Nirmala Sitharaman under the Ministry of Tribal affairs.

Objective

In the present study an effort has been given to analyse role of budget allocation as the developmental approach by the government at various stages and in various forms for the holistic development of PVTGs of Jharkhand in particular.

Research Methodology

The main source of information is the budget report of 2023-24. Many government and non-government organizations have released information and made it accessible both online and offline. The above mentioned data were utilized in this work. Through organizations like the Office of the Registrar General of India (census reports), secondary data is accessible (census report). This document has also used the records and reports available from the Ministry of Tribal Affairs, the National Sample Survey Office (NSSO), annual reports from several State Tribal Research Institutes, NGOs, Journals, books etc.

Issues of PVTGs

The lifestyle of PVTGs can not be regarded as good in the socio-economic context. Because it is not compatible with that of other communities. Slowly the social situation of PVTGs has slightly improved and continued to improve through different provisions of government.. Their way of life is slowly changing in the last decades which were not seen before that. The Children of the PVTG family are able to attend school. But the majority of them opt to work because of the family responsibility upon their shoulders. Due to their ignorance, they are taken advantage by middlemen. To combat this issue, GOI established a Conservation cum Development (CCD) initiative to support PVTGs people and enable them to work while simultaneously preserving the forest. There might be several issues among PVTGs which are not being resolved, but some of them which are quite common.

Unequal Implementation or Treatment through schemes: In certain circumstances, a PVTG only benefits in a small portion of a district, while the same group suffers in neighbouring blocks. The cause is that microprojects only provide advantages to those who fall under their purview. The Lanjia Sauras, for instance, are recognized as a PVTG across Odisha, but only two blocks had micro-projects developed, and these blocks are the only ones that receive benefits, while the remaining Lanjia Sauras are considered as Scheduled Tribes (STs)(Singh S. S., 2017).

Insufficient baseline surveys hampering the welfare programs:Out of 75 PVTGs, the Anthropological Survey of India found that baseline surveys are available for roughly 40 groups even after they have been designated as PVTGs. The implementation of community-focused welfare programs has been hampered by this.

Non-Update in the PVTGs list: It has caused name repetition and overlap. Such as the Mankidi as and the Birhor in Odisha, both relate to the same tribal group but are listed twice in the PVTGs list of Central Government.

Population Growth among Few PVTGs, like the Birhor in central India, continue to see stagnant population growth. Some, like the Onge and Andamanese, are also in decline.

Loss of their traditional means of subsistence, ecosystems, and resources: as a result of industrial projects, tourism, the indifference of the forest administration, climate change, deforestation, and other factors. The majority of PVTGs experience poverty, which can result in hunger, malnutrition, bad health, illiteracy, etc.

Education: In comparison to other tribal groups, these communities, particularly the women, have relatively poor educational level. Compared to other cultures, the literacy rate of primitive tribes is quite low. Presently, about 38.99 percent of PVTGs are literate.

Health: The infant mortality rate (IMR), hunger, and other chronic illnesses including leukaemia and skin conditions are all quite high and widespread.

Infrastructure: Insufficient access to clean water, unsanitary living conditions, hazardous terrain, and nutritional and medical services. The survey found that most families lacked their own home in numerous areas. The homes built by prehistoric tribal members lack adequate lighting and ventilation. Families with pets, such as goat or sheep owners, typically confine them to a corner of the home, at least during the rainy season. The family and the members share the area with the animals. Their vulnerability has increased due to their rights' non-recognition and ignorance (S.C., 2019).

Union Budget 2023-24 and Development from Past

The Union Budget of a year, commonly known as the annual financial statement, is a declaration of the expected income and expenditures of the government for that specific year. As per Article 112 of the Indian Constitution, it is compulsory for the government of India to present the annual financial statement about the estimated income and expenditure each year. This year Union Budget get announced on February 1, 2023. The government's financial records are kept by the Union Budget for the fiscal year, which runs from 1 April to 31 March. Revenue Budget and Capital Budget are two categories for the Union Budget. The government's revenue budget reflects both its income inflows and expenditures. While Capital budget of the includes Government capital payments and revenues (Times, 2023).

This financial statement provides the map of work which will be done during the next financial year. This year the special focus over the Tribal Development including Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups have attracted the intellectuals to analyse the reason behind the fund allocation. In process of recent interventions from government of India are the three most important programme (Finance, 2023) announcement regarding the development of tribal community of India are:

1. Pradhan Mantri Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups Development Mission

The current strategy for the holistic development of particularly vulnerable tribal groups was outlined in the recently passed union budget for 2023–2024. (PVTGs) The finance minister announced the beginning of the Pradhan Mantri PVTG Development Mission in order to enhance the socioeconomic circumstances of the especially vulnerable tribal groups (PVTGs). By doing this, essential amenities including secure housing, access to clean water and sanitation, better health and nutrition, road and telecommunication connectivity, and chances for sustainable livelihoods would be provided to PVTG families and habitations. The finance minister added that under the Development Action Plan for the Scheduled Tribes, Rs. 15,000 crores will be made available over the course of the following three years to carry out the Mission. Apart from the Ministry of Tribal Affairs, 41 Ministries/Departments are allocating funds under the Tribal Sub-Plan (TSP), now known as the Development Action Plan for Scheduled Tribes (DAPST), in the range of 4.3 to 17.5 percent of their total scheme allocation each year for tribal development projects related to education, health, agriculture, irrigation, roads, housing, electrification, employment generation, skill development, etc. Since 2013–14, the amount of DAPST funds allocated has grown by around five and a half times (from Rs. 21,525.36 crore (Actual Expenditure) in 2013–14 to Rs. 1,17,943.73 crore in Budget Estimate 2023–24).

2. National Sickle Cell Elimination

Additionally, the finance minister made a declaration that his department will take a proactive stance in addressing the integrated prevention, treatment, and management of the hereditary disease sickle cell. Together with the ICMR and the States in question, this will be carried out by the Ministries of Health and Family Welfare and Tribal Affairs.

3. Central Recruitment of Teachers for EMRSs

For the more than 750 Ekalavya Model Residential Schools (EMRSs), which will serve 3.5 lakh tribal kids, a total of 38,000 teachers and support personnel must be hired in the upcoming years. In order to give ST children in rural regions access to chances in high-quality educational programs and to get jobs in a variety of fields, EMRS was founded in 1997–1998. The holistic development of the kids is a priority for the schools in addition to academic instruction. There are 480 students allowed in each school, which serves students in grades VI through XII. Until now, the State Governments received subsidies under Article 275 (1) of the Constitution for the building of schools and recurrent expenditures.

Ongoing interventions

4. The Scheme for the Development of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs):

The Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) Development Scheme went into force on April 1, 2008. As per this scheme, the PVTGs are the Scheduled Tribes that considers to be the most vulnerable, result of which the Scheme prioritizes their development and protection for their sustainability. The Scheme allows state government freedom in developing programs that are tailored to the particular socio-cultural imperatives of the relevant groups in order to take a comprehensive approach to the socio-economic development of PVTGs. It is a flexible program that covers funding for initiatives like social security, including Janshree Bima Yojana, housing, land distribution, land development, agricultural development, animal husbandry, link road construction, installation of unconventional sources of energy for lighting, and any other cutting-edge activity intended for the comprehensive socio-economic development of PVTGs. Only actions that are necessary for the survival, protection, and development of PVTGs and not already covered by any other scheme of the national or state governments are eligible for funding. Each state, as well as the administration of the Andaman and Nicobar Islands, is required to create a long-term Conservation-cum-Development (CCD) plan that is valid for a period of five years for each PVTG on its territory. This plan must outline the initiatives the state will take, the financial planning for those initiatives, and the agencies tasked with carrying those out. An Expert Committee that is formed by the Ministry of Tribal Affairs approves the CCD Plan. The Central government then provides all of the funding for the Scheme. In accordance with the Special Central Assistance to Tribal Sub-Scheme, Article 275(1) of the Constitution, and the rules governing the use of funds therein, the funds under this scheme may only be used for vital activities that

are necessary for the survival, protection, and development of PVTGs. These activities must also not be specifically addressed by any other State or Central Government scheme. The State Government implements the program through Integrated Tribal Development Agency (ITDA)(Singh D. A., 2017). The funds released in previous 8 financial years as per the Ministry of Tribal Affairs can be seen below in table 1.1 and figure 1.1(Lakshman, 2023).

Serial No.	Financial Year	Funds released (in crores)	Utilisation reported (in crores)
1.	2016-17	338	319.96
2.	2017-18	239.49	223.19
3.	2018-19	250.00	250
4.	2019-20	249.99	249.99
5.	2020-21	140	140
6.	2021-22	250	160
7.	2022-23	252	124.79
8.	2023-24	256.14	-----

Figure 1.1: Funds utilisation for the PVTGs development in previous 8 years

The goal of the PVTG Growth Plan is for the PVTGs to experience complete socioeconomic development while preserving their culture and history. Under the program, the States/UT get financial support for things mentioned below (Saruta, 2021):

- Livelihood

- Employment opportunities and economic development through Agricultural development, Animal husbandry, Horticulture, Dairy, skilling and vocational training
- Education
- Health
- Strengthening of infrastructure through construction of community assets, like safe drinking water facilities including preservations and development of springs and underground water
- Sanitation facilities
- Recognition of habitat rights under section 3(1) e of the Forests Right Act-2006 and development of land forest resources
- Social security
- Housing and habitat in concept of preserving traditional architecture
- Installation of non-conventional sources of energy for lighting purpose
- Any other innovative activity meant for the comprehensive development of PVTGs.

5. PVTGs Dakia Yojana (Raj, 2016)

As Jharkhand is having 3rd highest population of PVTGs in states rank of India as per census report 2001. The population distribution of PVTGs in Jharkhand is 3,87,358 with having 09 PVTGs group. An innovative welfare program called PVTGs Dakia Yojana was created to offer social protection to PVTGs households. This program aims to offer social protection from two different types of dangers. Its **primary goal** is to help PVTGs manage the negative impacts of threats to economic instability. It plans to do this in three ways: -

- (i) The program offers 35 kilos of rice, which is the main meal for PVTGs, at no cost.
- (ii) It relieves PVTGs of the financial burden of travel expenses by guaranteeing that the rice is delivered to their door.
- (iii) By making sure that the rice is brought to the door, the program gives PVTGs the ability to carry out their daily-wage duties and make money, which they would otherwise have to forgo if they were to go to TPDS fair pricing stores.

Secondly, the Dakia Yojana aims to shield the families of PVTGs from the dangers of poverty and destitution. It does it in two ways:

- (i) First, by sparing PVTGs from the physical suffering they would have experienced if they had to go to TPDS fair pricing stores, the program achieves its goal.
- (ii) Two, the program helps PVTG's households meet their nutritional needs by giving them food grains and ensuring their physical well-being.

The program also avoids the health risks that would have occurred if their dietary demands hadn't been met. In addition, the program aims to give SHG members financial stability by offering them a respectable line of work in the form of packing food grain packages for door-to-door delivery. In accordance with this program, packages of 35 kg of rice are to be given to PVTG families. Mahila Sakhi Mandals and rural Self-Help Groups (SHGs) are to produce these packets. The National Rural Livelihood Mission's Jharkhand State Livelihood Promotion Society (JSLPS) sponsors these, Sakhi Mandals. For uplifting the PVTGs in holistic manner, there is the monitoring mechanism (Delhi, 2019) put in place is as detailed below: -

- (i) Utilization Certificates are required as a condition for further fund releases in accordance with General Financial Rules (GFR) guidelines;
- (ii) Progress reports on the status of scheme implementation are obtained.
- (iii) Officers visiting States/UTs check on the Ministry of Tribal Affairs' various programs' implementation progress.
- (iv) Meetings/conferences are held at the central level with State officials to ensure timely submission of applications.
- (v) The physical improvement of works endorsed under the schemes including "Development of PVTGs" is checked through online system of Ministry of Tribal Affairs - <http://stcmis.gov.in/smis> herein real time data has to be uploaded by the State Government.

Expected Outcomes and People Perceptions

Priority should be given to targeted efforts that address the core causes of high poverty and poor education of PVTGs and eliminate spatial obstacles to facility-based treatment. They must be linked with more comprehensive measures to lessen socio-economic mortality disparities in order to have an impact at the population level of the PVTGs. Community-based solutions can lessen many of the concerns and problems described above by reaching

out to underprivileged communities(Sophie L.P. Busch, 2022). One of the best impacts over the changing lifestyle of the PVTGs in India were because of interventions in Education Sector. Education is one of the important factors in socialisation system of human beings. One of these crucial systems is the educational system. In the contemporary era, decisions about the economic, social, and political realms have been made in large part as a result of education. The traditional economic system, culture, customs, mores, and practices are often found in rural economies. Due to education, these old structures have undergone clear transformation. Therefore, a major factor in socioeconomic development and change is education. A child's basic necessity is education. In spite of everything, the actual picture is not what it should be. Many people live their whole lives without ever attending school, both in India and many states like Guajrat, Madhya Pradesh, Jharkhand etc. The level of education in primitive tribal societies is quite low. In his 18th report, the Backward Class Commissioner made it abundantly plain that rapid educational expansion is essential for the betterment and development of scheduled tribal people in order to integrate them into society at large. Education and communication abilities are the cornerstones of economic progress. (Pancholi, 2018). The literacy rate (see table 1.2) of them has increased significantly during 2001 and 2011(Reddy, 2020). The Government Interventions with the help of many developmental organisation is leading towards the positive change in the lifestyle of PVTGs. This financial year has more expectation regarding the positive socio-economic growth in the tribal community. The rate of change in the educational status is very slow but the recent announcement in the budget 2023-24 about the recruitment will be game changer for the Tribal Development under the scheme of 'Ekalavya Model Residential Schools'.

S.No.	PVTGs (Numbers Statewise)	Literacy Rate (2001) in percentage	Literacy Rate (2011) in percentage
1.	Bihar and Jharkhand(09)	20.7	39.5
2.	Odisha(13)	-----	24.04
3.	Andhrapradesh and Telangana(12)	26.20	37.57
4.	Gujarat(05)	26.09	38 (Approx. in 2005)
5.	Karnataka(02)	-----	64.4
6.	Kerala(05)	26.10	51.86 Estimated on the basis of three PVTGs
7.	Madhya Pradesh	24.80	35.55

	and Chhatisgarh(07)	Estimated on the basis of four PVTGs	Estimated on the basis of four PVTGs
8.	Maharashtra(03)	-----	41.7 Katkaria Tribe only
9.	Rajasthan(01)	-----	18.27
Total Literacy (Average)		24.78	38.99

As far as the people's perception is concerned, it cannot be ignored easily, the failure of many programmes and schemes during the implementation phase has robust the people perception in negative way. One of the sad examples was PVTGs Dakia Yojana. The PVTGs Dakia Yojana was started with the intention of ensuring that food grains were delivered to the PVTGs families' doorsteps so they could avoid the physical and financial hardship of traveling. The research as per Rohan (2017) indicates that the program absolutely failed to achieve this goal. As PVTGs did not really receive their rice delivered to their doorstep in any of the blocks. Along with this, purchasing kerosene, salt, and sugar from TPDS stores is still required of PVTGs. As a result, PVTGs currently have to spend two days of the month in order to receive all of their entitlements since they must spend one day purchasing packets of rice from Targeted Public Distribution System (TPDS) stores or from locations close to the village. Additionally, some of these households must drive far to TPDS sellers the next day if they choose to purchase kerosene, salt, or sugar from fair pricing stores. The reason for this is that typically the days when rice is provided under the Dakia Yojana and the days that TPDS stores are open are different. Families from PVTG are discouraged from purchasing kerosene, salt, and sugar from stores with reasonable prices as a result. Instead, people pay more to purchase these items from any general shop. This was one of the factors that contributed to the majority of beneficiaries he spoke about not purchasing kerosene, salt, and sugar from stores that provide reasonable prices. This does not, however, mean that the plan was a total failure. PVTGs continue to gain from it in a number of ways. More than 70,000 PVTG families are already receiving food grains as a result of the implementation of this program, even if it is not being delivered directly to their home. AAY ration cards have already been distributed to almost all of the PVTGs families. As a result, they consistently receive 35 kilos of rice, albeit not at the proper time. The main cause of this is that dealers used to deprive them of food or provide them insufficient amounts of rice, but now BSOs/MOs are in charge of delivering the rice. These PVTGs families are thus no longer vulnerable to Dealer manipulation. In addition to this, the program offers rural women in need of work possibilities. Additionally, it has evolved into a constant source of income for SHG members.

In this manner, the program aids in the economic empowerment of rural women who handle the task of repackaging rice. Therefore, it can be concluded that the Dakia Yojana still has a long way to go before it succeeds completely and achieves all of its goals, but even at this point, it is having a lot of beneficial effects on the lives of its intended beneficiaries.

Conclusion

The challenges and issues faced by the PVTGs are very crucial over the past few decades. For recognizing their rights and reacting to government-led socio economical, sociocultural, educational and health related efforts. They are somewhat protected from exploitation and domination due to changing norms. The educational and health needs of these populations would be addressed through the use of creative, and collaborative approaches. The majority of the PVTGs' socio-economic and socio-cultural issues would be resolved in addition to providing better health care services and education with the help of recent announcement of PM PVTG Development Mission. Intensifying measures to enhance housing, sanitation, employment opportunities, access to healthcare, and better road transportation infrastructure would ultimately improve the standard of living in tribal populated regions. Even though the significant progress made by PVTGs in terms of the aforementioned accomplishments is reason for the satisfaction. Immense amount of work must be done with a greater emphasis on the numerous unresolved issues like poverty, illiteracy, livelihood and migration, unavailability of drinking water and sanitation facilities, lack of health care facilities, all-weather roads and affordable transportation, discrimination and exploitation. Budget 2023 has given priority for PVTGs development. The above mentioned schemes will be helpful to eradicate all the impoverishment of PVTGs in the coming years as per the government's will.

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